

IMPACT RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH TOUGHENED EPOXY MATRICES

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1 Introduction

The combination of high specific strength, corrosion resistance and low radar signature make composite sandwich structures an attractive structural choice for many disciplines including the naval sector. The characteristics of composite sandwich structures have many benefits including reduction of fuel and maintenance costs across the lifespan of the vessel [1]. However, the brittle nature of composite materials can lead to substantial overdesign of sandwich structure components, counteracting their weight and cost savings benefits. Naval vessels are unique, in that they have to withstand both structural loads as well as explosive blast and impact loadings. The toughness of a composite material, a critical parameter for a material to withstand blast loading, can be improved by improving the toughness of the individual components of the sandwich structure. Previous work by this group has demonstrated that by altering the layup of the individual plies in the composite skins, a significant increase in impact resistance of the structure can be obtained [2]. This abstract builds on this work further and details a systematic study of the effect of increasing the toughness of the matrix material in the composite skins on the impact resistance of a sandwich structure. The transfer of toughness from the bulk polymer which acts as the matrix, through to a carbon fibre laminate and finally into the composite sandwich structure.

2 Experimental Methods

2.1 Materials

An amine-cured epoxy system formed the basis of all the materials investigated in the current work. Seven formulations of epoxy resin with systematically increasing amounts of polysiloxane core-shell rubber (CSR) nanoparticles and silica nanoparticles were

prepared. The bulk polymer panels of each formulation were manufactured alongside carbon fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite panels and full sandwich structures. All panels adopted a layup from bi-axial non-crimp carbon fibre. The composite and sandwich structure panels were manufactured using resin infusion. The epoxy foam core used had a nominal density of 170 kg/m³ and was manufactured using PB170 foaming epoxy resin and DM03 amine based hardener provided by Sicomin. The foaming took place in an aluminium mould lined with a self adhesive polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) coated glass fabric for ease of release.

2.2 Methods

Of the bulk polymer properties, modulus and ultimate strength were evaluated through both tension and plane strain compression tests, while the single-edge-notched bend specimen was employed to evaluate fracture energy. Double cantilever beam (DCB) tests were performed in order to determine the interlaminar fracture energy of the CFRP composites.

High velocity impact experiments were performed using a gas gun apparatus accelerating a hemispherical aluminium projectile, as used by Rolfe et al. [2]. The velocity of the projectile was recorded by two infrared sensors located towards the end of the gas gun barrel exit. The panel was contained within a polycarbonate and aluminium safety box and two high-speed cameras were located behind the panel outside of the safety box. To facilitate digital image correlation (DIC), the panels were spray painted matt white and a random black speckle pattern was applied to the back surface of the panel.

The properties of the epoxy foam were tested according to ASTM D1621-16 [3]. Samples with dimensions of 30x30x30 mm cubes were tested, cut from the same panels used in the sandwich cores to

allow recording of varying foam densities and yield strengths. The viscosity of epoxy resin is sensitive to temperature. As a direct consequence of this the foamability and final density of the epoxy foam is also sensitive to temperature. As a result, all foaming took place in a custom built temperature controlled environment. This allowed close monitoring of the influence of temperature during the foaming process.

3 Results

The fracture energy, G_{Ic} , of each of the bulk polymers is given in Figure 1. The addition of rubber nanoparticles to the epoxy resin was found to greatly increase the toughness of the bulk resin. The measured values of the mean mode-I initiation, $G_{Ic,init}(comp)$ inter-laminar fracture energies are also given in Figure 1 for comparison. The benefits of nano-modification of the composite matrices can be clearly observed, as the CFRP composites with the modified epoxy matrices exhibit significantly higher values of $G_{Ic,init}(comp)$. From these tests, the transfer of toughness from the bulk polymer to the CFRP laminate is clear. However, there is a limit to the effectiveness of the toughening of a CFRP laminate as discussed by Carolan et al. [4] whereby the toughening mechanisms of the nano particles ahead of the crack tip, such as void growth, are restricted by the nearby fibres.

A typical uniaxial compressive stress-strain curve for the epoxy foam manufactured is shown in Figure 2, the curve is typical of an elastic plastic rigid foam. The yield of the foam is taken as the maximum stress below 10% strain. The samples were tested parallel to the rise direction and any skin was removed.

4 Conclusion

The addition of nanoparticles to the epoxy resulted in orders of magnitude increase in toughness. This also manifested in the toughness of the carbon fibre laminates and has implications for the dissipation of kinetic energy in a sandwich structure in ballistic impact tests.

5 References

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Fig. 1. Comparison of the values of the measured initiation fracture energies of the CFRP composites and bulk polymers.

Fig. 2. Uniaxial compressive stress versus strain for a typical epoxy foam sample.